

1 **A comparative assessment of treatment methods to release ferulic acid from Brewer's**
2 **Spent Grains**

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11

12 **Abstract**

13 Brewers' spent grain (BSG) is the main byproduct from the brewing industry, which accounts for
14 85% of the total waste generated during beer production. This lignocellulosic material is
15 traditionally used as livestock feed and sold at a low price. However, BSG can be used as a low-
16 cost feedstock for the production of bioactive molecules and chemicals precursors, upgrading the
17 value of this byproduct. In this context, BSG is a promising feedstock for the extraction of
18 antioxidants like ferulic acid (FA) and *p*-coumaric acid (*p*-Cu). The effectiveness of three
19 hydrolysis treatments were evaluated for the extraction of FA and *p*-Cu from BSG, namely
20 enzymatic, alkaline and hydrothermal. The hydrothermal treatment produced the highest
21 extraction yields (7.2 g/kgBSG and 1.4 g/kgBSG for FA and *p*-Cu, respectively) in a short
22 extraction time (an hour). On the other hand, enzymatic hydrolysis extracted 4.3 g/kgBSG for FA
23 and negligible yields for *p*-Cu in 4 h of incubation at 25 °C. Yields of 5.5 g/kgBSG for FA and 0.6
24 g/kgBSG for *p*-Cu were obtained in more than 5 h of alkaline treatment (2 M NaOH) at 120 °C.
25 The mass and energy balances herein conducted revealed the high dependence of the operating
26 costs on the concentration of BSG used during the extraction process, with costs of 34.5 €, 6607

27 € and 205.5 € per kg of FA for the chemical, enzymatic and hydrothermal extraction methods,
28 respectively, at 100 kg BSG/m³.

29 **Keywords**

30 Brewer's spent grain; chemical treatment; coumaric acid; enzymatic treatment; ferulic acid;
31 hydrothermal treatment.

32 **Introduction**

33 The valorization of by-products from the food and beverage (F&B) industry is critical for the
34 environmental and economic sustainability of the sector. The beer sector ranks among the top
35 F&B industries, with a sustained annual production of 1.9-2 billion hectoliters at a global level over
36 the past 10 years. Brewer's spent grain (BSG) is the main secondary stream that remains after
37 wort production during the beer brewing process. While the wort generated is used in the
38 fermentation process, the BSG is not further utilized in the brewing process [1], [2]. The brewing
39 sector generates 20 kg of BSG per hl of beer, making up to \approx 85% of all waste produced by the
40 brewing industry. This BSG is currently used as feedstock in animal nutrition, but its rapid
41 deterioration because of water content limits the potential commercialization of this beer
42 byproduct [3]. BSG can be also converted into biogas and compost. However, the current BSG
43 valorization pathways entail a low revenue compared to its potential to generate higher added
44 value products.

45 In this context, BSG is an excellent source of phenolic compounds, which are known for their anti-
46 inflammatory, anti-carcinogenic and anti-apoptotic qualities[4]. Since the presence of a free
47 hydroxyl group is necessary to stabilize free radicals, BSG phenolics are primarily found in barley
48 husk, where they concentrate in the cell walls and esterify to sugar residues. These conditions
49 reduce their antioxidant activity[5]. The majority of the hydroxycinnamic acids in BSG are phenolic

50 compounds, ferulic acid (FA) and *p*-coumaric (*p*-Cu) being the most abundant and main
51 responsible of the antioxidant potential of cereals.

52 FA can be utilized to manufacture biovanillin or as an ingredient in nutraceuticals. Although there
53 is a rising demand for FA derived from natural sources, this bioproduct has only recently been
54 used in the cosmetic industry due to the need to optimize its production at large scale [6], [7]. On
55 the other hand, *p*-Cu is another phenolic acid of great interest due to its chemoprotectant and
56 antioxidant properties [8] Antioxidants prevent rancidity development in food, preserve its
57 nutritional value, increase its shelf life, and possess multiple benefits in human health. Today, the
58 quest for natural antioxidant sources to successfully replace synthetic ones, which have been
59 recently linked to harmful and cancer-causing effects, is a topic of great industrial interest [9].

60 However, the extraction of antioxidants from BSG requires an effective disruption of its crystalline
61 structure that enables its fractionation. BSG has a complex and recalcitrant nature of
62 lignocellulosic waste, whose composition includes cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin [10]. In this
63 context, the optimization of energy and reagent consumption is necessary for a cost-effective
64 industrial-scale implementation of green techniques for antioxidant extraction from BSG.

65 Alkaline and enzymatic hydrolysis are conventional treatments to extract added value products
66 from BSG [11]. Alkaline hydrolysis represents nowadays the easiest, cheapest and most popular
67 method to release ferulic acid from agro-industrial by-products [12], [13], [14]. In addition, some
68 authors have even pretreated lignocellulosic materials with diluted H₂SO₄ prior NaOH addition to
69 effectively remove hemicellulose and then solubilize lignin to separate the ester-bound FA and *p*-
70 Cu from BSG [15]. However, the treatment time of alkaline hydrolysis is typically long and
71 consumes high amount of reagents. The sample must be neutralized after treatment and the lignin
72 structure is altered [16].

73 On the other hand, enzymatic hydrolysis has shown to be a very effective and environmentally
74 friendly technique. Mainly because it does not generate hazardous residues after antioxidant
75 extraction [17], [18]. Due to the heterologous nature of the polysaccharides present in BSG,
76 enzymes break down arabinoxylan (AX) and sidechain-acting enzymes are necessary to allow
77 main-chain-acting xylanases to more easily reach the polymers[19]. These enzymes have the
78 ability not only to deconstruct plant biomass, but also to synthesize novel bioactive components
79 for use in health and pharmaceutical industries. However, the enzymatic hydrolysis of BSG using
80 commercial enzyme preparations typically present low recovery yields of FA and *p*-Cu, which
81 requires further research [20], [21].

82 Hydrothermal hydrolysis use only water as a reaction medium, and therefore is considered as an
83 environmentally friendly alternative to conventional chemical extraction processes [22]. This
84 technique releases firstly acetyl groups by hydrolyzing the acetylated hemicellulose fraction. This
85 “self-acidified” technique is called autohydrolysis. The resulting acetic acid molecules cleave
86 hemicellulosic glycosidic linkages and decrease their degree of polymerization. In addition, the
87 autohydrolysis promotes the cleavage of hemicellulose – lignin bonds, which enhances the
88 access to the target extraction products (i.e FA or *p*-Cu). In this context, subcritical water
89 extraction (SubCW-H) has been proposed as an alternative to alternative to traditional methods
90 methods based on their superior extraction yields and sustainable operating conditions [23]. This
91 method is nowadays considered as a “green technique” due to its compliance with the
92 requirements of most international regulatory agencies [17], [24]. The benefits of SubCW-H
93 include its eco-friendliness, just uses water, low operating costs, and its ability to carry out
94 selective extractions (mimicking traditional herbal decoction for preparing herbal medication but
95 with a higher extraction efficiency). Additionally, SubCW-H has been found to be a highly efficient
96 and rapid method for extracting bioactive compounds from multiple recalcitrant biomasses,
97 making it an environmentally friendly alternative to conventional extraction methods based on

98 organic solvents such as methanol and ethanol[25]. The implementation of subcritical water
99 extraction in Sudden Expansion Micro-Reactors (SEMR) is an innovative alternative to obtain
100 antioxidants from BSG. The ability of the SEMR to rapidly stop the reaction allows the release of
101 FA and *p*-Cu from BSG, and Avoids the stage of rapid degradation and propagation of secondary
102 reactions. Despite the merits of SubCW-H and SEMR, this technology has never been tested for
103 the extraction of FA and *p*-Cu from BSG, until now.

104 In this work, a comparative assessment of the efficiency of chemical, enzymatic and subcritical
105 water hydrolysis on FA and *p*-Cu extraction from BSG was conducted. In addition, a preliminary
106 analysis of the energy demand and operational costs of the three extraction methodologies was
107 herein conducted.

108 **Materials and methods**

109 **Brewer's spent grain**

110 Two industrial breweries in Copenhagen (Denmark) and Canarias (Spain), namely Carlsberg and
111 Compañía cervecera de Canarias, respectively, provided the BSG used in this research. The
112 feedstock was procured directly from the elaboration of the beer and kept frozen at -20 °C until
113 usage in the lab. The BSG was thawed, cleaned with purified water and further dried at 80°C
114 overnight. The dried BSG was grinded using an IKA® MF10 basic microfine grinder to a particle
115 size of 0.4 mm, then stored at room temperature until further processing or analysis.

116

117 **Process description**

118 The extraction processes for production of FA and *p*-Cu using chemical, enzymatic and
119 hydrothermal treatments are summarized in Fig. 1

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124 B

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129 **Fig.1:** Simplified scheme of the A) chemical, B) enzymatic and C) hydrothermal treatment for
 130 FA and p-Cu recovery.

131 **Alkaline extraction**

132 The antioxidants alkaline extraction procedure consisted of an acid pre-treatment with an aqueous
133 solution of 72 % H₂SO₄ w/w at 120 °C for 15 min. 20 mL of H₂SO₄ solution were mixed with 50 g
134 of BSG. At the end of the reaction, the solid residue was separated by centrifugation at 10.000 g
135 for 15 minutes, washed with water until neutral pH was reached and dried at 50 ± 5 °C. This solid
136 residue (10 gr of pellet) was then treated with 20 mL of a 2% sodium hydroxide solution at 40 °C
137 for 4 hours at 200 rpm. The first supernatant was obtained after 20 minutes of centrifugation at
138 10.000 g. The NaOH treatment was repeated, and both supernatants were pooled for FA and *p*-
139 Cu determination by UHPLC. In addition, the total phenolic concentration (TPC) was estimated in
140 the supernatants as described below. The experiments were performed in triplicate.

141

142 **Enzyme extraction**

143 A combination of the enzymes *AnFae1* (UniProtKB-A2QSY5), originating from *Aspergillus niger*
144 CBS 513.88 (*An*), and an endoxylanase from *Dickeya zeae* Ech586, classified within the family
145 GH30 and obtained as described previously in Smith et al. 2021 [26]. BSG (20 kg/m³) was pre-
146 incubated with sodium acetate (10 mM pH 6) as a buffer at 25 °C under agitation for 15 min before
147 adding the enzymes at concentrations of 1 μM and 0.1 μM, respectively. Subsequently, the BSG
148 was treated with the cocktail of the enzymes at 25 °C for 4 hours under continuous shaking at
149 1000 rpm. The insoluble fraction of the BSG was removed by centrifugation at 14000 g for 3 min.
150 The remaining enzymes in the supernatant were inactivated at 100 °C for 20 min and cooled on
151 ice prior FA and *p*-Cu determination by UHPLC. The TPC was characterized in the supernatants.
152 The experiment was performed in triplicate.

153

154 **Subcritical water hydrolysis**

155 The BSG was treated by hydrothermal processes to determine the influence of the subcritical
156 medium and reaction times on the valorization of the brewery by-product. A 11,3% w/w BSG
157 suspension was fed to the hydrothermal treatment system (described in Cantero et al. 2014), and
158 mixed with a stream of water at subcritical conditions (15MPa and 280°C) at a ratio 2,2:1. These
159 subcritical water conditions resulted in reaction conditions of 210°C and 15MPa, with a reaction
160 time of approximately of 2,0 seconds. At the end of the reactor, an expansion valve allowed a
161 sudden reduction in temperature and pressure of the BSG broth in order to instantaneously stop
162 any further reaction. The FA and *p*-CU concentrations in the treated effluent were quantified by
163 UHPLC along with TPC. The experiment was performed in triplicate.

164 **Mass and energy balances**

165 Mass and energy balances accounted for the requirements of raw materials (BSG and solvents),
166 consumables (chemical, enzymes) and energy needs (electricity). In this context, the electricity
167 required for the operation of the hydrolysis reactors, agitation and centrifuges was taken into
168 account. To complete the mass balance in the process units using experimental yields, a
169 stoichiometric approach was considered. Operating costs were calculated using an electricity cost
170 of 0.289 €/kwh for industrial purposes according to the European regulatory market.

171 Equation 1 can be used to estimate the total economic cost for each extraction procedure

$$172 \text{ Total cost } (\text{€}/\text{m}^3) = \text{material} + \text{consumables} + \text{cost of electricity of unit operation} \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

173 Where the term “material” corresponds to BSG (with a negligible cost for the market) and water
174 (1.91 €/m³) for the 3 treatments. In the particular case of the enzymatic treatment, the
175 consumables were the cocktail of the enzymes needed for the extraction calculated by multiplying
176 the concentration of the enzymes required per m³ of BSG solution and the market price of Feruloil
177 esterase (450 €/kg enzyme) and xylanase (45 €/kg enzyme), as reported by Fabian et al., 2010
178 [27]. In the chemical treatment, the consumables referred to the chemical reagents were

179 calculated by multiplying the concentration of NaOH and H₂SO₄ required for the extraction of BSG
180 and their corresponding market price (0.12 €/kg NaOH and 0.03 €/kg H₂SO₄). In the hydrothermal
181 treatment, no consumables were required. The cost of the electricity (€/m³) for each of the unit
182 operation (Fig 1) used was calculated according to Eq 2, Eq 3, Eq 4 and Eq 5.

183 Equation 2 describes the electricity cost for stirring in the chemical treatment:

$$184 \text{ Stirring (€/m}^3\text{)} = \text{cost of electricity (0.289 €/Kwh)} \times \text{specific power consumption for the stirring (4} \\ 185 \text{ Kw/m}^3\text{)} \times \text{Duration of stirring (h)}. \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

186 Equation 3 describes the electricity cost of the centrifuges used in the enzymatic, chemical and
187 hydrothermal treatment for separation of the solid BSG fraction:

$$188 \text{ Centrifugation (€/m}^3\text{)} = \text{cost of electricity (0.289 €/Kwh)} \times \text{specific power consumption for} \\ 189 \text{ centrifugation (3 Kwh/m}^3\text{)} \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

190 Equation 4 estimates the electricity cost of the operation of the hydrolysis reactor used for
191 enzymatic treatment

$$192 \text{ Hydrolysis reactor (€/m}^3\text{)} = \text{cost of electricity (0.289 €/Kwh)} \times [\text{specific power consumption for the} \\ 193 \text{ stirring (1.5 Kw/m}^3\text{)} \times \text{Duration of stirring (h)} + \text{Energy for heating}/\eta \times \text{ER} \\ 194 \text{ (Eq. 4)}$$

195 Where η is the efficiency of conversion of electricity into thermal energy (0.99) and ER is the
196 efficiency of energy recovery in the heat exchangers (to pre-heat the fresh BSG solution) (0.7).

197 Equation 5 determines the electricity cost of the reactor used in the hydrothermal treatment

$$198 \text{ Hydrothermal reactor (€/m}^3\text{)} = \text{cost of electricity (0.289 €/kWh)} \times \text{specific power requirement of} \\ 199 \text{ the hydrothermal reactor (504.3 kW/m}^3\text{)} \times \text{Duration of reactor operation (h)} + \text{cost of electricity} \\ 200 \text{ (0.289 €/Kwh)} \times \text{specific power consumption for centrifugation (3 Kwh/m}^3\text{)} \\ 201 \text{ (Eq. 5)}$$

202 Finally, the cost per unit of FA for each treatment was calculated according Eq. 6

203 Cost of FA (€/kgFA) = Total cost of treatment / ([BSG] / Y_{FA/BSG}) (Eq. 6)

204 Where the total cost of each treatment was described in Eq 1 (€/m³), [BSG] is the concentration
205 of BSG (kg of dried BSG/m³) and the Y_{FA/BSG} is the yield of FA (kg FA/kg of dried BSG). A sensitivity
206 analysis of the influence of the initial concentration of BSG (ranging from 10 to 1000 kg of dried
207 BSG/m³) on the operation cost (€/kg FA) was conducted using the three extraction procedures.

208 The extraction yields for each treatment ranged from 5 to 6 g FA/kg BSG for chemical hydrolysis,
209 from 3.8 to 4.7 g FA/kg BSG for enzymatic hydrolysis and from 6 to 8.5 g FA/kg BSG for
210 hydrothermal hydrolysis.

211

212 Analytical procedures

213 UHPLC was used to quantify FA and *p*-Cu concentration (Dionex UltiMate 3000 UHPLC system
214 equipped with a Diode Array Detector (DAD) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Sunnyvale CA, U.S.A.,
215 AmaZon SL, Bruker Daltonics, Bremen, Germany). The UHPLC analysis was carried out in an
216 ODS-L Optimal column (250 cm × 2.1 mm × 5 m) from Capital UHPLC Ltd. (Broxburn, Scotland,
217 U.K.) at a flow rate of 0.2 mL/min, a pressure of 96 bar and a column temperature of 40 °C. The
218 mobile phase consisted of 0.1% formic acid in water (83.6%) as eluent A and acetonitrile (16.4%)
219 as eluent B. The injection volume was set at 5 µL. The electrospray was set to negative scan
220 mode with the following parameters: capillary voltage of 4.5 kV, end plate offset of 0.5 kV,
221 nebulizer pressure of 3.0 bar, dry gas flow of 12.0 L/min, and dry gas temperature of 280°C. A
222 Bruker Compass Data Analysis v.5.2 (Bruker Daltonics, Bremen, Germany) was used for data
223 handling and peak integrations. The retention time was checked using authenticated standards,
224 while gravimetric calibration was performed solely on FA and *p*-Cu. FA and *p*-Cu concentration
225 was estimated using a computed correlation between MS intensity (peak area) and UV-vis
226 detection response at two wavelengths (nm): 316 and 225 nm using a UV detector at 276 nm.

227 TPC was estimated via colorimetric assay using Folin-Ciocalteu (FC) reagent following [28]. A
228 calibration curve using different concentrations of gallic acid as standard was used to estimate
229 the total phenolic content present in the liquid samples after the treatments of extraction using the
230 Folin-Ciocalteu reagent (Sigma Aldrich, Spain). The plates were then incubated in the dark for 30
231 minutes at 40 °C. Following incubation, the absorbance was measured at 765 nm in a
232 spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-2550). The results were expressed in milligrams of gallic acid
233 equivalent per gram dry weight (mg GAE/g BSG dw) BSG.

234 **Statistical Analysis**

235 Triplicate experiments were performed and the results were expressed as average \pm standard
236 deviation. A statistical significance ($p < 0.05$) analysis was done by one-way ANOVA and
237 compared using Tukey's model. Data processing was performed using Microsoft Excel 2016®
238 (Redmond, WA, USA) and SPSS version 22.0® (IBM Corp., NY, USA).

239 **Results and discussion**

240 **Total Phenolic Content**

241 The TPC released after the extraction from the BSG in the different treatments accounted for 9.5
242 \pm 0.2, 5.1 \pm 0.2 and 15.0 \pm 0.4 mg GAE/gBSG, using chemical, enzymatic and hydrothermal
243 extractions, respectively. Recent studies have shown TPC in a lower range (0.83–1.40 mg GAE/g
244 substrate) in crude extracts (before the hydrolysis) of BSG [29]. In this context, the hydrolysis of
245 the rigid lignocellulosic structural components to release the phenolic acids is critical. Alkali
246 hydrolysis is commonly used with BSG and similar recalcitrant substrates. The TPC of the
247 hydrolyzed liquid fraction of BSG following acidification and partitioning is often reported, which
248 is approximately four times higher than the TPC values of the crude extracts. Interestingly, the
249 TPC of the hydrothermal extraction liquid fractions from BSG, averaging 15.00 mg GAE/gBSG,

250 was significantly higher than those recorded during chemical and enzymatic extractions. Birsan
251 et al., 2019 reported lower ranges of TPC in the BSG using alkaline treatments and extractions
252 with solvent as ethyl acetate compared with this study (2.8-3.8 mg GAE/gBSG). The higher
253 efficiency of the hydrothermal treatment was attributed to the higher level of hydrolysis of the
254 hemicellulose-cellulose-lignin complex. This hydrolysis will promote the release of ferulic acid,
255 usually cross-linked with lignin and hemicellulose. In addition, the high temperature used in this
256 treatment likely mediated a positive effect on the extraction yield of TPC due to an enhanced
257 solubility and diffusivity of phenolic compounds [30], [31]. On the other hand, the release of
258 polyphenols during the enzymatic treatment can be expected to occur as a combined result of the
259 saccharification of structural polymers of BSG generating only specific products [30].

260 **Quantification of ferulic and p-coumaric acid from BSG**

261 Most of the phenolic compounds in the barley grain are contained in the husk, and therefore, the
262 lignocellulosic BSG (mainly composed of cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin) represents a rich
263 source of natural antioxidants and also a low-cost alternative to synthetic antioxidants [32]. The
264 pretreatments of milling and homogenization of the substrate herein applied to the BSG grains
265 helped to break down the lignocellulosic material and improve the efficiency of the extractive
266 process [33].

267 In the chemical treatment, BSG was initially pre-treated with dilute sulfuric acid to solubilize the
268 hemicellulosic fraction, which was further reacted with NaOH. Thus, hemicellulose removal
269 increased material porosity and facilitated the diffusion and impregnation of the NaOH into the
270 substrate in the subsequent steps [14]. Some studies have reported that a fraction of the lignin
271 (14 % w/w) is also solubilized during acid pre-treatment and the rest is solubilized with the alkali
272 treatment, resulting in liquors containing FA and *p*-Cu [2]. The UHPLC analysis of the hydrolysate
273 produced by chemical hydrolysis of BSG revealed the presence of FA (5.5 ± 0.6 g FA/Kg BSG,

274 corresponding to 550 mg/l FA in the hydrolysate) and *p*-Cu (0.6 g ± 0.1 *p*-Cu/Kg BSG,
275 corresponding to 60 mg/l). According to Mussatto et al. (2007) [15], concentrations of FA and *p*-
276 Cu of ~ 145 mg/l FA and 139 mg/l *p*-Cu, respectively, were found under optimal operating
277 conditions (2.0% NaOH concentration, 120 °C, 90 min) in the chemical hydrolysate after BSG
278 extraction. Hagos et al. (2021) reported yields of 0.46 g/kg BSG for FA using a chemical pre-
279 treatment at 2% NaOH concentration and 120°C for 90 min. These authors also observed a direct
280 correlation between the extraction time and the extraction yield during the first 140 min of
281 incubation, while longer extraction periods induced a decrease in the FA yield. This decrease in
282 the concentration of FA, which is susceptible to heat, temperature and other oxidizing agents,
283 was attributed to the oxidation of this antioxidant when a solvent is applied over an extended
284 period of time.

285 In the enzymatic treatment, a bacterial feruloyl esterase (*AnFae1*) was herein tested together with
286 a xylanase (GH30) for the specific release of FA and *p*-Cu from BSG. The cocktail of enzymes
287 was initially optimized in terms of enzyme dosage and incubation time of enzymatic hydrolysis in
288 the recovery of the antioxidants. A high concentration (> 80% of the initial FA content) was
289 obtained during enzymatic treatment (4.30 ± 0.6 g FA/ kg BSG). Similarly, Bartolomé et al. (1997)
290 [34] observed that the esterase from *Aspergillus niger* (*An*) was able to release only 3.3% of the
291 total FA from BSG. They also observed that the cocktail with a xylanase from *Trichoderma viride*
292 could increase the release of FA from BSG, but the concentration obtained was only a 30% of the
293 total FA recorded in our study [35]. On the other hand, cultures from *Streptomyces avermitilis*
294 CECT 3339 released 43% of the total FA in BSG [36]. Similarly, extraction yields of 1.89 g FA/kg
295 BSG in the first extraction and 0.50 g FA/g BSG in the second extraction were reported using
296 commercial enzymes such as Depol 740L [37]. Interestingly, *p*-Cu was not released from BSG
297 structure during the enzymatic hydrolysis since it was not their primary substrate. In our particular

298 work, the feruloyl esterase in combination with xylanases broke down the ester bonds between
299 arabinose and FA side groups, thus releasing FA.

300 The maximum yield of FA and *p*-Cu during the hydrothermal treatment of BSG accounted for 7.2
301 ± 1.1 g FA/kg BSG and $1.4 \text{ g} \pm 0.6$ *p*-Cu/kg BSG, respectively. Subcritical water has been used
302 to release FA from lignocellulosic feedstocks, including BSG, wheat bran, rice bran and distillery
303 stillage. Recent research has shown that subcritical water extraction (operating at 185°C) is
304 effective at releasing FA and other phenolic compounds from these materials, but in lower
305 concentrations (0.14 g FA/kg rice brand and 0.6 g *p*-Cu/Kg rice brand) [38]. In this context,
306 research on the subcritical water treatment of defatted rice bran and distillery stillage also
307 demonstrated the release of phenolic compounds such as FA. Indeed, subcritical water has been
308 shown to be effective in releasing FA from various agricultural by-products [27]. This treatment
309 was designed to reduce the equipment cost by developing compact devices with short operating
310 times: changes in residence time from minutes to milliseconds allowing to reduce the reactor
311 volume from m^3 to cm^3 . Particularly, high temperature pressurized water has proved to be an
312 effective and sustainable solvent for clean, safe and environmentally benign organic reactions. In
313 addition, SEMR technology allows to lower the temperature in a fraction of a second by generating
314 high-pressure steam that can be energetically integrated with the general biomass treatment
315 process [36]. This paper constitutes the first application of SubCW-H-SEMR for the extraction of
316 antioxidants such as FA and *p*-Cu.

317 **Techno-economic analysis**

318 The chemical treatment required more than 5 hours at 120°C in the hydrolysis tank and entailed
319 an energy consumption of 16.5 kWh/ m^3 for a BSG solution of 100 kg BSG/ m^3 . Thus, the operating
320 costs of the process accounted for 18.95 €/ m^3 BSG (Eq. 1), which corresponded to 34.45 €/Kg
321 FA and 315.85 €/Kg *p*-Cu (Eq. 6). A decrease in the total extraction cost of FA (€/ Kg FA) from
322 BSG by 80% was observed when BSG concentration increased from 10 kg/ m^3 to 1000 kg/ m^3

323 according to the sensibility analysis conducted (Fig 2A). On the other hand, the enzymatic
324 treatment involved an incubation of 2 hours at 25°C, with a total energy consumption in the
325 hydrolysis tank of 4 kWh/m³ BSG at 100 kg BSG/m³. This process entailed an operation cost of
326 2973 €/m³ BSG (Eq. 1) or 6607 €/ Kg FA (Eq. 6). The sensibility analysis performed revealed a
327 low dependence of the operating cost with BSG concentration, which exhibited a decrease from
328 6607 to 6600 €/ Kg FA when BSG concentration increased from 10 to 1000 kg BSG/m³ (Fig 2 B).
329 Finally, the hydrothermal treatment applied for the antioxidant extraction process operated at
330 reactor reaction time of approximately one hour with a total energy consumption of approximately
331 507.34 kW/m³ at a BSG concentration of 100 kg/m³. The subcritical water hydrolysis consumes
332 water and energy, not any other chemical. As for the energy consumption, the system allows
333 energy integration by preheating the water with the reactor outlet stream. The actual
334 experimentation conditions were assumed for these calculations. The subcritical water is
335 preheated up to 100°C by using the reactor product depressurized down to atmospheric pressure.
336 If pressure was higher after the reactor, higher temperatures would be achieved and more energy
337 integration would be possible. At this BSG concentration, the SWE-SEMR would entail an
338 operating cost of 147.96 €/m³ BSG or 205 €/kgFA and 1056 €/p-Cu, respectively. In this particular
339 technology, an increase in BSG concentration from 10 kg/m³ to 1000 kg/m³ entailed a decrease
340 in the operating cost of FA extraction from 205 €/kgFA to 20 €/kgFA (Fig 2 C)

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345 **Fig 2:** Influence of the initial concentration of BSG on the operation cost (€/kg FA) of the A)
 346 chemical B) enzymatic, C) hydrothermal treatments. Standard deviations represent the cost
 347 variation according to the range of empirical extraction yields.

348 Overall, the SubCW-H -SEMR treatment represents a sustainable, simple, compact and effective
 349 method for the extraction of antioxidants from BSG. SubCW-H -SEMR enables the recovery of
 350 antioxidants at a larger extent than chemical and enzymatic processes. Although the chemical
 351 treatment turned out to be the most economical, it requires both a high chemical consumption
 352 and long extraction times (exceeding 48 h in some studies), and a significant energy consumption
 353 at large-scale [36]. On the other hand, enzymatic methods require shorter reaction times but
 354 expensive consumption of enzymes, which endangers the economic sustainability of this
 355 biological process.

356 **Perspectives and Challenges**

357 Innovative techniques such as SubCW-H -SEMR devoted to the extraction of antioxidants from
 358 brewer's spent grain supported a superior performance in terms of FA and *p*-Cu yields,

359 operational times, and solvent and energy consumption, compared to traditional extraction
360 methods such as chemical and enzymatic processes. The operational costs of SubCW-H -SEMR
361 were significantly lower than the market prices of FA and *p*-Cu (~ €4,000/Kg for FA and
362 ~€16,700/Kg for *p*-Cu). Unfortunately, SubCW-H -SEMR requires complex equipment capable of
363 operating at high pressures and temperatures, which increases process complexity and
364 investment costs compared to conventional treatments [39].

365 The commercial application of BSG antioxidant extracts still presents social perception
366 challenges, despite the fact that their antioxidant potential has been extensively documented and
367 their mechanisms of action are today well understood. In addition, the poor stability, rapid
368 degradation and oxidation of these antioxidants currently limit their potential applications for the
369 manufacture of cosmeceutical products. Furthermore, limited research has been conducted on
370 the permeability of the extracted natural antioxidants, like those from BSG, in human skin layers.
371 There are few reports in literature suggesting that phenolic compounds, such as *p*-Cu and FA,
372 exhibit a limited skin permeability in conventional cosmetic formulations for human models.
373 Therefore, the development of more efficient delivery strategies, such as compound
374 nanoencapsulation and formulations with permeation enhancers, is necessary to fully exploit the
375 commercialization potential of FA and *p*-Cu from BSG [40], [41].

376 **Conclusion**

377 In this work, the efficiency of three different methods for the extraction of two of the most abundant
378 antioxidants present in BSG, FA and *p*-Cu, was evaluated. The highest FA yield was achieved for
379 the hydrothermal treatment, followed by the chemical and enzymatic treatments (7.2> 5.5>4.3 g
380 FA/kg BSG). Interestingly, *p*-Cu was only released by the chemical and hydrothermal treatment
381 (0.6 and 1.4 g *p*-Cu/kgBSG). A preliminary techno-economic analysis estimated operating costs
382 of €34.5, €6607 and 205 € per kg of FA for the alkaline, enzymatic and hydrothermal treatments
383 at a BSG concentration of 100 kgBSG/m³. These operating costs strongly depended on the BSG

384 concentration, stabilizing above 300 kgBSG/m³ in the hydrothermal and chemical treatment. In
385 brief, SWE-SEMR emerged as the most promising alternative for the recovery of antioxidants
386 from BSG in terms of efficiency and operating cost.

387 **Declaration of Competing Interest**

388 The authors have no conflict of interest to declare.

389 **Acknowledgments**

390 The authors wish to thank the breweries ABBA and Compañía Cervecera de Canarias for kindly
391 supplying raw BSG samples and Jane W. Agger and Jesper Holck for their technical support in
392 the MS analysis.

393 **Funding**

394 This work was supported by the BiOBreW project, which is funded by the European Union's
395 Horizon MSCA 2021-PF-01 research and innovation programme, under grant agreement N°
396 101065428. The Regional Government of Castilla y León and the EU-FEDER programme (CL-
397 EI-2021-07 and UIC 315) are also gratefully acknowledged.

398 The authors acknowledge the Agencia Estatal de Investigación for the financial support given in
399 Project TED2021-129837B-C42. This work was supported by the Regional Government of
400 Castilla y León (Spain) and the EU-FEDER program (CLU-2019-04). Danilo Cantero is funded by
401 the Spanish Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities ("Beatriz Galindo" fellowship
402 BEAGAL18/00247).

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